

1 **Evolving resistance patterns in *Tetranychus urticae* and *Bemisia tabaci* in Greece**

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16 **Running Title:** Evolving resistance in *T. urticae* and *B. tabaci* in Greece

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21 Greek populations of *T. urticae* and *B. tabaci* exhibit evolving multi-resistance, confirmed by
 22 bioassays and molecular markers, highlighting the urgent need for evidence-based resistance
 23 monitoring in IPM.

24

25 **ABSTRACT**

26 **BACKGROUND:** Pesticide resistance in agricultural pests remains a major barrier to effective
27 and sustainable crop protection. In this study, we assessed the current resistance status of two key
28 pests, *Tetranychus urticae* and *Bemisia tabaci*, in major agricultural regions of Greece. A total of
29 25 field populations were collected between 2023 and 2025 and tested using single-dose bioassays
30 and droplet digital PCR (ddPCR) for target-site resistance mutations. \

31 **RESULTS:** The results revealed significant variability in susceptibility to multiple acaricides and
32 insecticides. Several *T. urticae* populations displaying reduced sensitivity to abamectin,
33 hexythiazox, and fenpyroximate. Resistance mutations such as I321T (GluCl3), I1017F (CHS1),
34 F1538I (VGSC), and G126S (cytb) were detected simultaneously at high frequencies in a number
35 of *T. urticae* populations, indicating multi-resistant phenotypes. A widespread occurrence of
36 F331W (ace1), L925I/T929V (VGSC), and A2083V (acc) mutations were recorded in *B. tabaci*,
37 showing the dynamics of resistance to organophosphates, pyrethroids, and ketoenols, respectively.
38 **CONCLUSION:** Our findings underscore the ongoing evolution of resistance in these pests and
39 highlight the need for integrated management strategies that include regular resistance monitoring
40 and judicious pesticide use. This study provides resistance surveillance data to guide pest control
41 decisions and promote sustainable Integrated Pest Management (IPM) in Greece.

42

43 **KEYWORDS**

44 Pesticide resistance; *Tetranychus urticae*; *Bemisia tabaci*; Molecular diagnostics; Green
45 Pesticides; Integrated Pest Management (IPM)

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47

48 1. INTRODUCTION

49 The emergence and fast spread of pesticide resistance in agricultural pests is a major threat to crop
50 protection and food production. Resistance has been recorded in many arthropod species around
51 the world and is often linked to the repeated use of insecticides. Two of the most important pests
52 globally, the two-spotted spider mite (*Tetranychus urticae*) and the silverleaf whitefly (*Bemisia*
53 *tabaci*), are especially known for their ability to develop resistance to several groups of pesticides.
54 According to the Arthropod Pesticide Resistance Database ¹, there are currently 558 reported cases
55 of resistance for *T. urticae* and 898 for *B. tabaci*.

56 In Greece, these pests are serious threats for many vegetable, fruit, and ornamental crops, both in
57 greenhouses and in open fields. Integrated Pest Management (IPM) strategies are increasingly
58 promoted as a holistic approach to pest control, encouraging the use of biological control agents,
59 crop rotation, resistant cultivars, and environmentally friendly alternatives. Among these, the use
60 of “green chemicals” or biorational pesticides—products derived from natural sources such as
61 plant extracts, microbial metabolites, or naturally occurring fatty acids—has gained ground in
62 recent years. These compounds are considered to have low toxicity to non-target organisms and a
63 lower risk for resistance development, and their integration into IPM programs is actively
64 encouraged ²⁻⁴. Nevertheless, chemical control remains the main method currently used in the field,
65 particularly against *T. urticae* and *B. tabaci*.

66 The diversity and intensity of these applications contribute to strong selection pressure and
67 accelerated resistance evolution. Several pesticide groups with different Modes of Action (MoA)
68 are applied, including neonicotinoids, sulfoximines, and butenolides (which act on nicotinic
69 acetylcholine receptors), abamectin (targeting the glutamate-gated chloride channels GluCl_s),
70 pyriproxyfen (a juvenile hormone analog), hexythiazox, a mite growth inhibitor (MGI) targeting

71 the chitin synthase CHS1, Mitochondrial Electron Transport Inhibitors (METI) like pyridaben,
72 fenpyroximate, and acequinocyl, and diamides (affecting the ryanodine receptor). Due to their
73 frequent use, resistance has been developed in many field populations of *T. urticae* and *B. tabaci*
74 ⁵⁻¹⁷. One of the main mechanisms of resistance in these pests is the presence of mutations in the
75 target sites of pesticides.

76 In *T. urticae*, several known mutations have been associated with resistance: I1017F in the CHS1
77 gene (for MGIs like hexythiazox and etoxazole), F1538I and L1024V in the voltage-gated sodium
78 channel (VGSC) gene (linked with pyrethroid resistance), G126S, H92R, P262T and S141F in the
79 mitochondrial cytochrome b gene (for resistance to METI-I and METI-III acaricides), and G314D,
80 G326E, and I321T in the GluCl genes (for abamectin resistance) ^{5,18-21}.

81 In *B. tabaci*, several resistance mutations have also been reported. These include the F331W
82 mutation in the *ace1* gene (linked to resistance to organophosphates and carbamates) ²², the L925I
83 and T929V mutations in the VGSC gene (for pyrethroid resistance) ^{15,23}, and the A2083V mutation
84 in the *acc* gene (associated with resistance to ketoenols like spiromesifen) ²⁴. In addition, the
85 A387G mutation in the cytochrome P450 gene *CYP6CMI* has been associated with neonicotinoid
86 resistance (Pym et al., 2023), along with recently identified mutations in the $\beta 1$ subunit of the
87 nicotinic acetylcholine receptor (*nAChR* $\beta 1$) gene ²⁵. To improve monitoring and resistance
88 detection, droplet digital PCR (ddPCR) was recently developed as a highly sensitive molecular
89 method to monitor the presence and frequency of resistance mutations with high accuracy and
90 sensitivity ^{9,10}, in pooled insect and mite DNA samples.

91 In this study, we present bioassay and molecular monitoring resistance data for *T. urticae* and *B.*
92 *tabaci* field populations collected from major crops and agricultural regions of Greece, collected
93 between 2023 and 2025. Novel molecular assays were developed and applied for resistance

94 mutations such as *A387G* in *CYP6CM1* and *A58T* in *BTβ1*. The results are discussed in the light
95 of evidence-based insecticide resistance management (IRM) and integrated pest management
96 (IPM) strategies.

97

98 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

99 **2.1 *Tetranychus urticae* and *Bemisia tabaci* field samples**

100 A total of 19 field populations (Table 1) of *Tetranychus urticae* (Tu1–Tu19) and 6 populations of
101 *Bemisia tabaci* (Bt1–Bt6) were collected from different areas of Greece between September 2023
102 and January 2025. Sampling was carried out from infested leaves of various host plants mainly
103 vegetables and citrus, collected from greenhouse and open fields. Collection areas included major
104 agricultural zones in Southern Greece such as the Peloponnese (Achaea, Argolida, Messinia) and
105 Crete (Heraklion and Lasithi prefectures).

106 Four *T. urticae* populations were collected from citrus crops (lemon, orange, tangerine), 14
107 populations were collected from vegetables (cucumber, zucchini, tomato, eggplant, melon,
108 watermelon, pepper), and one population in a garden growing rose. For several populations,
109 pesticide application history was known and included a wide range of compounds. In particular,
110 Tu5 (from pepper/eggplant in Tympaki) had a history of treatments with spinetoram, spinosad,
111 metaflumizone, formetanate, and acrinathrin. Tu9 (from eggplant in Messinia) was treated with
112 pyriproxyfen, acetamiprid and flonicamid, while Tu11 (from watermelon in the same area) had
113 been treated with abamectin. Tu12 (from melon) was exposed to acetamiprid and
114 chlorantraniliprole, Tu16 (zucchini) to pyriproxyfen, and Tu18 (zucchini) to hexythiazox and
115 acequinocyl and fatty acid potassium salts. For the rest of the populations, either no chemical

116 treatments had been applied (Tu1, Tu4, Tu6, Tu7, Tu8, Tu17, Tu19) or the pesticide history was
117 unknown (Tu2, Tu3, Tu10, Tu13, Tu14, Tu15).

118 The *B. tabaci* populations were collected mainly from solanaceous and cucurbit crops such as
119 eggplant, tomato, pepper, cucumber and melon. In this case, pesticide use was recorded for several
120 samples. Bt1 (eggplant, Tympaki) had been exposed to flonicamid, acetamiprid, pyridaben,
121 pyriproxyfen, and sulfoxaflor; Bt2 (tomato, Tympaki) to azadirachtin, acetamiprid, and
122 pyriproxyfen; Bt5 to cyantraniliprole, sulfoxaflor, pyriproxyfen, pyridaben and deltamethrin.
123 Although the Bt6 (eggplant, Tympaki) field was known to be untreated during the sampling period,
124 it had a heavy history of chemical applications. In the remaining cases (Bt3, Bt4), the treatment
125 history was unknown.

126 **2.2 Toxicity assays**

127 Mortality assessment was performed for *Tetranychus urticae* with four acaricides/insecticides of
128 different MoA, abamectin (Vertimec 18EC, MoA: GluCl allosteric modulator), bifenazate
129 (Floramite 240SC, MoA: METI-III), fenpyroximate (Kento 5.12SC, MoA: METI-I) and
130 hexythiazox (Nissorun 25SC, MoA: MGI) using diagnostic recommended field doses (RD). In
131 addition, toxicity assays at the RFD were conducted with three “green” non-conventional chemistry
132 formulations, namely Requiem, Eradicoat, and FLiPPER. Requiem is a botanical extract of the plant
133 *Chenopodium ambrosioides* and contains a variety of terpenoids as active ingredients. The active ingredient
134 of Eradicoat is maltodextrin, that is derived from decomposed potato starch. FLiPPER is a natural extract
135 of olive oil and contains potassium salts, composed of unsaturated carboxylic acids. In all cases adulticidal
136 bioassays were conducted with 25 2-3 days old adult female mites which were transferred on the
137 upper side of 9 cm² square-cut kidney bean leaf discs on wet cotton wool. The plates were sprayed
138 with 1 ml of spray fluid at 1 bar pressure with a Potter Spray Tower (Burkard Scientific, UK) to
139 obtain a homogenous spray film. The toxic effects of hexythiazox were assessed with egg

140 bioassays, by having 20 adult females laying eggs on a leaf disc for 5h, as previously described
141 (REF). After spray treatment, leaf discs were placed at 25 ± 0.5 °C, 60% RH and 16:8 h (light:dark)
142 photoperiod. Three replicates were sprayed per dose and, as a control, deionized water was used.
143 Mortality was assessed after 72h for abamectin, bifenazate, fenpyroximate, Requiem, Eradicoat
144 and FLiPPER. Adult mites were considered alive if they could walk twice the distance of their body
145 size after being prodded with a fine hairbrush. Mites treated with hexythiazox were considered
146 unaffected, if they displayed the same developmental stage as the water treated control at the time
147 of scoring. The percentage mortality resulting from exposure to each insecticide was calculated
148 after being corrected for control mortality. The percentage mortality for each insecticide was
149 corrected using Schneider-Orelli's formula, i.e., Corrected % mortality = [(mortality % in
150 treatment- mortality % in control) / 100 - mortality % in control)] x 100.

151 **2.3 Genomic DNA isolation and quantification**

152 Genomic DNA extractions were performed on pools of adult mites, following the CTAB method
153 as previously described ²⁶. The concentrations of extracted gDNAs were determined with the
154 Qubit™ dsDNA BR Assay (Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA) on a Qubit fluorometer 2.0 (Invitrogen,
155 Carlsbad, CA), to obtain measurements specific for double stranded DNA (dsDNA). The mean \pm
156 SE dsDNA concentration for *T. urticae* pools was 12.2 ± 3.76 (range: 4.6–25.0 ng μL^{-1}), while
157 for the *B. tabaci* pools 77.9 ± 19.85 (range: 11.0–140.0 ng μL^{-1}).

158 **2.4 Droplet Digital PCR (ddPCR) Assays**

159 Droplet digital PCR (ddPCR) was performed using the QX200 Droplet Digital PCR System (Bio-
160 Rad, Hercules, CA, USA), as previously described ^{9,10} Each 20 μL reaction contained 1 \times ddPCR
161 Supermix for Probes (no dUTP) (Bio-Rad), 5 U of EcoRI-HF® restriction enzyme (New England

162 Biolabs), 5 ng of genomic DNA, and primers and probes specific to each mutation. Probes were
163 labeled with FAM for mutant alleles and HEX for wild-type alleles.

164 Droplets were generated with the QX200 droplet generator and thermocycled under the following
165 conditions: 95 °C for 10 min, followed by 50 cycles of 94 °C for 30 s and 54–60 °C for 1 min, and
166 a final step at 98 °C for 10 min. After amplification, droplets were read on the QX200 droplet
167 reader, and data were analyzed using QuantaSoft™ Analysis Pro Software (v1.0.596).

168 The limit of detection (LoD) was determined using synthetic gBlock™ controls and reached 0.1–
169 0.2%, depending on the assay. This sensitivity allows for reliable detection of low-frequency
170 resistance alleles in pooled samples. Details on assay characteristics, including primers and probe
171 sequences for previously published mutations, are available in Mavridis et al.^{9,10}. In addition, novel
172 TaqMan ddPCR assays were developed for the detection of the *A387G* mutation in the *CYP6CMI*
173 gene and the *A58T* mutation in the *BTβ1* gene.

174 For *A387G*, the primers used were: Bt_387_F: GTCTGTTTCAGAGACGCTGCGBt_387_R:
175 GTGCACGTCCGCACCAA and Probes: Bt_387_Pwt (wild-type): HEX-CTGTACCCGGCGTC-
176 MGBBt_387_Pmut (mutant): FAM-CGACCCCGGGTAC-MGB. For *A58T*, the primers were:
177 Bt_58F: GCAGAACATCACTGAGAAGGTTGA Bt_58R:
178 TTTGTAAGACTCCGTTTTTATTTCTGA and Probes: Bt_58_Pwt (wild-type): HEX-
179 TTCGGGCTGGCTTT-MGBBt_58_Pmut (mutant): FAM-ATTCGGGCTGACTT-MGB.

180 **2.5 Statistical analyses**

181 The limit of detection (LoD) for each ddPCR assay was defined as the lowest MAF that could be
182 reliably detected with accuracy calculated according to ²⁷. The mutant allelic frequency (MAF)
183 was calculated as: %MAF = [Mutant copies / (Mutant + Wild-type copies)] × 100.

184

185 3. RESULTS

186 3.1 Toxicity assays

187 Toxicity assays were conducted on twelve field populations of *Tetranychus urticae* to evaluate
188 their response to four acaricides with different MoA: abamectin (GluCl allosteric modulator),
189 bifenazate (METI-III), fenpyroximate (METI-I), and hexythiazox (MGI). The majority of the
190 populations were collected from vegetables (eight out of twelve) while the remaining four
191 populations (Tu1-Tu4) originated from citrus orchards. The results revealed strong variability in
192 acaricide efficacy among populations (Table 2).

193 Most tested populations (Tu1–Tu4, Tu6, Tu11–Tu14) exhibited high levels of susceptibility to all
194 four compounds, with corrected mortality values ranging from 87.57% to 100%. However, three
195 populations (Tu5, Tu9, and Tu10) showed reduced sensitivity to multiple acaricides. Tu5 showed
196 especially low mortality to abamectin (36.99%), fenpyroximate (9.46%), and hexythiazox
197 (14.44%) and low to moderate mortality to bifenazate (63.46%), suggesting resistance to several
198 chemical groups. Similarly, Tu9 and Tu10 showed very low mortality to hexythiazox (0.33% and
199 0.28%), abamectin (24.6% and 13.10%) and fenpyroximate (28.83% and 19.66%), indicating
200 multiple resistance traits.

201 Among the tested products, bifenazate was the most effective acaricide across the evaluated
202 populations, consistently achieving 100% mortality in all except one (Tu5), where a moderate yet
203 significant reduction in efficacy was observed (63.46%).

204 Five *T. urticae* populations were also tested against three alternative "green" products: Requiem,
205 Eradicoat and FLiPPER (Table 3). Population Tu3 derived from citrus while the remaining four
206 populations (Tu5, Tu9, Tu10 and Tu14) are from vegetables. In general FLiPPER and Requiem
207 were the most effective products, producing >70% mortality in four out of five populations.

208 Population Tu10 showed high susceptibility to all three products, with mortality rates above 90%.
209 Tu9 and Tu14 both showed high mortality to Requiem and FLiPPER (100%), but their response to
210 Eradicoat was lower, with Tu9 showing reduced mortality (43.47%) and Tu14 showing a moderate
211 response (71.93%). Tu3 showed moderate mortality to Requiem (74.64%) and Flipper (70.68%),
212 but a low response to Eradicoat (23.58%). Tu5 was the least responsive, with very low mortality
213 to Eradicoat (6.44%) and low response to Requiem (42.73%) and FLiPPER (39.27%).

214 **3.2 Detection of resistance mutations in *T. urticae* field populations**

215 Droplet digital PCR (ddPCR) analysis was used to quantify the frequency of resistance-associated
216 target-site mutations in 17 *Tetranychus urticae* field populations. The results revealed substantial
217 variability in resistance allele frequencies among populations and across different pesticides (Table
218 4).

219 Mutations associated with resistance to GluCl allosteric modulators (abamectin), including *G314D*
220 and *G326E* in *GluCl1* and *GluCl3* respectively, were absent in all populations (0% MAF). The
221 *I321T* mutation in *GluCl3*, also linked to abamectin resistance, was detected in eight populations,
222 in fixation (100%) in two populations (Tu9, Tu10), in high frequencies in Tu5 (54.45%), Tu16
223 (69.04%), and lower levels in Tu7 (30.04%), Tu8 (16.10%), Tu18 (10.07%), and Tu2 (0.39%).

224 For sodium channel modulators (pyrethroids), *F1538I* was widely present (8 populations), being
225 fixed or nearly fixed in Tu5 (100%), Tu9 (100%), Tu12 (100%), and Tu16 (92.33%). Intermediate
226 or lower frequencies were observed in Tu15 (31.41%), Tu19 (42.71%), Tu13 (4.64%), and Tu8
227 (1.65%). In contrary, *L1024V* was only detected at extremely low frequency in Tu1 (0.92%) and
228 Tu2 (0.74%) both originating from citrus.

229 The *I1017F* mutation in *CHSI*, conferring resistance to mite growth inhibitors (MGIs) such as
230 etoxazole and hexythiazox, was highly prevalent or fixed in five populations (Tu5, Tu9, Tu10,
231 Tu16 and Tu19), and present at very low levels in Tu1 (1.89%) and Tu2 (0.40%).
232 Regarding mitochondrial electron transport inhibitors (METIs), *H92R* (associated with METI-I
233 resistance) was detected at moderate frequency in populations Tu19 (47.77%) and at extremely
234 low frequency in Tu5 (0.74%). *G126S* was highly prevalent or fixed in Tu5, Tu9, Tu10, Tu16, and
235 Tu19 while found at low levels in Tu2 (0.41%). The *P262T* mutation was detected only in Tu19
236 (42.89%), while *S141F* was not detected in any population.
237 No resistance mutations were detected in four populations (Tu3, Tu4, Tu14 and Tu17) suggesting
238 that these populations are fully susceptible based on the tested markers. On the other hand, Tu5,
239 Tu9, Tu10, Tu16, and Tu19 harbored multiple high-frequency resistance mutations, indicating
240 multi-resistant phenotypes.

241 **3.3 Detection of resistance mutations in *B. tabaci* field populations**

242 Six *Bemisia tabaci* field populations (Bt1–Bt6) were screened using droplet digital PCR (ddPCR)
243 for key target-site resistance mutations associated with multiple insecticide classes (Table 5).
244 The *F331W* mutation in the *Ace1* gene, which confers resistance to acetylcholinesterase inhibitors
245 (organophosphates and carbamates), was detected at high frequencies in all populations except Bt3
246 (21.48%), ranging from 89.30% in Bt5 to 95.56% in Bt4. For pyrethroid resistance, both *L925I*
247 and *T929V* mutations in the *vgsc* gene were consistently detected. The combined MAFs for these
248 two mutations ranged from low in Bt3 (*L925I*: 2.90%, *T929V*: 10.73%) to high levels in Bt6
249 (*L925I*: 44.74%, *T929V*: 45.29%). The *A2083V* mutation in the *acc* gene, associated with
250 resistance to lipid biosynthesis inhibitors (tetronic and tetramic acid derivatives), showed strong
251 variation. It was found to have a very high frequency in five out of six populations (Bt1, Bt2, Bt4,

252 Bt4 and Bt5) ranging from 71.43% to 92.74% while detected at extremely low frequency in
253 population Bt3 (1.39%).

254 Among the tested populations, Bt6 appeared as the most resistant, showing the highest MAFs
255 across all tested classes: *F331W* (92.11%), *L925I/T929V* (44.74/45.29%), and *A2083V* (92.74%),
256 indicating multiple target-site resistance. In contrast, Bt3 exhibited the lowest MAFs, *F331W*
257 (21.48%), *L925I/T929V* (2.90/10.73%), and *A2083V* (1.39%), suggesting a more susceptible
258 profile.

259 None of the tested neonicotinoid resistance mutations-*A387G* in the *CYP6CM1* gene and *A58T* in
260 the *BTβ1* gene-were detected in any of the *B. tabaci* populations analyzed.

261

262 **4. DISCUSSION**

263 This study examined field populations of *Tetranychus urticae* and *Bemisia tabaci* from key
264 agricultural regions in Southern Greece, encompassing both mainland areas and the island of
265 Crete. These regions are marked by intensive fruit and vegetable cultivation-under both open-
266 field and greenhouse conditions-where pest control predominantly depends on repeated pesticide
267 applications. Such high-input practices impose strong selection pressure, accelerating the
268 emergence and spread of resistance in local pest populations.

269 Our study indeed, confirms the presence of widespread resistance in both species in Greece, with
270 strong associations between bioassay results and key resistance mutations. The toxicity data for
271 four acaricides (abamectin, bifenazate, fenpyroximate, and hexythiazox) demonstrated a wide
272 range of responses among *T. urticae* populations. Among the twelve populations tested, four
273 originated from citrus orchards and eight from vegetable crops. Citrus populations were almost
274 fully susceptible to all tested acaricides, whereas populations from vegetables showed varying

275 responses at the recommended field dose. Three populations from vegetables, collected in
276 Messinia (Peloponnese) and Tympaki (Crete), displayed low sensitivity to three or all four tested
277 acaricides, indicating multi-resistant phenotypes. The remaining five populations from vegetables
278 were fully susceptible to all tested compounds, consistent with the known pesticide use history in
279 the field. In our previous study ¹⁰, more than half of the tested populations were found to be multi-
280 resistant to the majority of acaricides. This difference may be attributed to the fact that those
281 populations were collected from Crete five years ago, from heavily treated greenhouse systems
282 growing vegetables and ornamentals.

283 Additionally, the toxicity of three “green” products (Requiem, Eradicoat, and FLiPPER) was
284 evaluated in five populations with different host plants and varying responses to synthetic
285 pesticides. One population was collected from citrus (Tu3), which was susceptible to all acaricides,
286 while four were collected from vegetables and included both multi-resistant (Tu5, Tu9, Tu10) and
287 susceptible (Tu14) populations. The efficacy of ‘green’ products varied and was not correlated
288 with that of ‘conventional’ acaricides. Requiem and FLiPPER, and to a lesser extent Eradicoat,
289 effectively controlled the Tu10 population, which was highly resistant to most conventional
290 acaricides tested. However, they failed to control another highly resistant population, Tu5.
291 Additionally, the highly susceptible Tu3 population from citrus showed no sensitivity to any of
292 the ‘green’ products. These results can be explained by the different modes of action—and
293 consequently different resistance mechanisms—of the ‘green’ products, highlighting their
294 potential as complementary tools within integrated pest management (IPM) schemes.

295 A panel of twelve target-site resistance mutations, previously developed and applied ¹⁰, was used
296 to detect resistance in *T. urticae*. These assays allowed us to identify multiple mutations associated

297 with resistance, some of which have also been linked to phenotypic resistance and provided useful
298 comparisons with previous findings.

299 Mutations in GluCl1 (G314D) and GluCl3 (G326E and I321T) have been strongly associated with
300 abamectin resistance ^{5,11,28}. Among the three, only I321T was detected in our study, in eight
301 populations with varying frequencies, whereas G314D and G326E were completely absent. In
302 populations Tu5, Tu9, and Tu10 - where both toxicity and molecular data were available - there
303 was a clear correlation between low mortality and high mutation frequency. Compared to our
304 previous study ¹⁰, where G326E alone or in combination with G314D was detected in four out of
305 six populations and associated with low mortality at RD (as low as 6%), the present data show a
306 shift toward the prevalence of I321T. According to Xue et al. (2020) ²⁹, the I321T mutation was
307 detected in red-morph *Tetranychus urticae* strains exhibiting resistance to abamectin, and a similar
308 mechanism could be relevant in the populations analyzed in the present study. It is also possible
309 that additional mutations in GluCl3 (V327G and L329F ²⁹) or the recently reported insertions in
310 GluCl2 ³⁰, which were not investigated here, may be present and contribute to the observed
311 resistance phenotypes.

312 F1538I and L1024V are known pyrethroid resistance mutations ^{17,31}. L1024V was detected at very
313 low frequency in only two citrus populations (<1%), while F1538I was more frequent, found in
314 nearly half of the tested populations and at high frequency in several cases. This prevalence is
315 consistent with our previous findings ¹⁰. Although pyrethroids are not registered against *T. urticae*
316 in citrus or vegetables, their use against other insect pests may explain the selection pressure and
317 the observed high frequencies in populations from vegetables.

318 The I1017F mutation in CHS1 was found at high frequency in populations with low hexythiazox
319 mortality, confirming its strong link to MGI resistance. It was found fixed in Tu5, Tu9, and Tu10,

320 all of which showed poor response to hexythiazox (mortality at RD below 15%). These results
321 agree with our previous study ¹⁰, where this mutation was detected at high frequency in half of the
322 populations and was also correlated with resistance to etoxazole.

323 H92R, a mutation in PSST associated with resistance to METI-I acaricides (e.g., pyridaben,
324 fenpyroximate), was detected in only two populations — one at moderate (48%) and one at very
325 low frequency (<1%). Interestingly, toxicity data showed low mortality to fenpyroximate in three
326 populations (Tu5, Tu9, Tu10), although the H92R mutation was not present. Previously ¹⁰, H92R
327 was frequently found in Crete populations, though it showed poor association with pyridaben
328 toxicity.

329 For bifenazate resistance, three *cytb* mutations (G126S, S141F, and P262T) were examined.
330 G126S was found at high or fixed frequency in several populations, while P262T was detected in
331 only one case, in combination with G126S. S141F was not detected in any sample. In our previous
332 study (Mavridis et al., 2022b), only G126S was detected, consistent with the current findings —
333 apart from Tu19, where P262T was also identified. To our knowledge, this is the first detection of
334 P262T in Greece and may reflect evolving resistance to bifenazate. Since previous research has
335 shown that G126S alone does not confer resistance ³² it is possible that the combination of G12S
336 (found in fixation in Tu5) with other mutations in *cytb* ^{33,34} could explain the reduced susceptibility
337 of this population to bifenazate.

338 The general agreement between molecular and bioassay data highlights the usefulness of these
339 markers, while observed differences from earlier studies suggest that resistance patterns may still
340 be evolving. These findings highlight the importance of regular monitoring to detect resistance
341 alleles at low frequencies and to make informed, adaptive decisions regarding the choice of
342 acaricides.

343 In *B. tabaci*, most populations carried multiple target-site mutations: F331W (ace1), L925I/T929V
344 (vgsc) and A2083V (acc). The F331W mutation, which was previously fixed in Crete populations
345 ¹⁷, was still present at high frequency (>89%) in all samples except Bt3 (21.48%).
346 Similarly, both L925I and T929V mutations were found at moderate to high frequencies in all
347 populations except Bt3. In our previous survey ⁹, L925I was more frequent than T929V, whereas
348 here T929V appears slightly more prevalent — possibly due to their mutually exclusive nature.
349 Earlier studies in Greece and other Mediterranean countries ^{35,36} have also reported high
350 frequencies of kdr mutations.
351 Decades of pyrethroid and organophosphate use against *B. tabaci* in Crete and the absence of major
352 fitness costs may explain the results for the high frequencies of mutations conferring resistance to
353 these groups of insecticides.
354 The A2083V mutation, associated with ketoenol resistance, was found at high to very high
355 frequencies (>71%) in five out of six populations, and at very low frequency in Bt3. In our previous
356 work, this mutation was detected in 8 of 11 populations, but usually at lower levels (>70% in only
357 3 populations). Although we did not perform spiromesifen bioassays in the current study, high
358 resistance levels against the compound has been documented in *B. tabaci* populations from Greece
359 ³⁷ and our earlier findings ⁹ support a strong genotype–phenotype link for A2083V.
360 Neonicotinoid resistance in *Bemisia tabaci* has been functionally associated with the
361 overexpression of CYP6CM1, which enhances the metabolic detoxification of neonicotinoid
362 molecules into less toxic derivatives ^{38,39}. In the present study, droplet digital PCR (ddPCR) assays
363 were developed to target recently reported mutations in the CYP6CM1 and nAChR_β1 genes ⁴⁰.
364 However, neither mutation was detected in any of the populations examined. This absence may be
365 attributable to the prohibition of neonicotinoids in open-field crops, including vegetables, since

366 2018 in Greece, following European Union legislation. Nevertheless, the molecular diagnostics
367 developed here represent a promising tool for future resistance monitoring programs.

368 Although this study focused on target-site resistance mechanisms, metabolic resistance — such as
369 overexpression of detoxification enzymes — is also known to play an important role in both
370 species^{18,41–43} and should be considered in future surveys.

371

372 **5. CONCLUSION**

373 This study reveals a complex and evolving resistance landscape in *Tetranychus urticae* and
374 *Bemisia tabaci* across major agricultural regions of Greece. Resistance patterns closely reflect
375 cropping systems and pesticide usage intensity, with populations from vegetable crops in Crete
376 and Messinia exhibiting higher levels of resistance compared to the more susceptible populations
377 from citrus orchards. This highlights the critical role of local agronomic practices in shaping
378 resistance dynamics and underscores the need for tailored pest management strategies across
379 cultivation zones.

380 The frequent co-occurrence of multiple target-site mutations within the same populations points
381 to widespread multi-resistance and declining efficacy of commonly used pesticides. These findings
382 reinforce the importance of integrating routine bioassays with molecular diagnostics to enable
383 early detection and informed decision-making in pest control. Resistance monitoring should be a
384 cornerstone of IPM programs, especially in high-input systems where resistance across several
385 mode-of-action classes is already entrenched.

386 Looking ahead, the sustainable management of these pests will require the adoption of innovative
387 tools such as biopesticides.

388 Combining conventional and emerging approaches within a coordinated, evidence-based
389 framework will be essential to preserve crop productivity and enhance agroecosystem resilience.

390

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402

403 **7. CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT**

404 The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest related to this work.

405

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549

9. TABLES

Table 1 Toxicity assays of four acaricides for ten *Tetranychus urticae* field populations from Greece

Acaricide class (active ingredient)	GluCl allosteric modulators (Abamectin)	METI-III (Bifenazate)	METI-I (Fenpyroximate)	MGI (Hexythiazox)
Population	Corrected Mortality at the recommended field dose (%Mortality \pm SE)			
Tu1	98.47 \pm 1.53	100.00 \pm 0.00	92.22 \pm 4.07	99.35 \pm 0.65
Tu2	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00	95.89 \pm 2.26	99.29 \pm 0.71
Tu3	100.00 \pm 0.00	96.33 \pm 1.89	87.97 \pm 5.12	100.00 \pm 0.00
Tu4	98.51 \pm 1.49	100.00 \pm 0.00	98.63 \pm 1.37	100.00 \pm 0.00
Tu5	36.99 \pm 1.18	63.46 \pm 9.67	9.46 \pm 1.35	14.44 \pm 2.09
Tu6	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00
Tu9	24.6 \pm 0.99	100.00 \pm 0.00	28.83 \pm 1.66	0.33 \pm 0.58
Tu10	13.10 \pm 1.56	100.00 \pm 0.00	19.66 \pm 1.07	0.28 \pm 1.38
Tu11	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00
Tu12	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00
Tu13	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00
Tu14	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00	100.00 \pm 0.00

Table 2 Toxicity assays of three green pesticides for five *Tetranychus urticae* field populations from Greece

Green pesticide	Requiem	Eradiocoat	Flipper
Population	Corrected Mortality at the recommended field dose (%Mortality \pm SE)		
Tu3	74.64 \pm 2.58	23.58 \pm 7.25	70.68 \pm 4.67
Tu5	42.73 \pm 15.94	6.44 \pm 5.41	39.27 \pm 8.90
Tu9	100.00 \pm 0.00	43.47 \pm 2.14	100.00 \pm 0.00
Tu10	91.97 \pm 1.74	95.83 \pm 1.62	100.00 \pm 0.00
Tu14	100.00 \pm 0.00	71.93 \pm 1.62	100.00 \pm 0.00

Table 3 Mutant allele frequencies measured by ddPCR in pools of field *T. urticae* populations (N = 50 individuals per pool)

Acaricide class (active ingredient)	GluCl allosteric modulators (Abamectin)			Sodium channel modulators (Pyrethroids)		MGI (Etoxazole/Hexythiazox)	METI-I (Pyridaben)	METI-III (Bifenazate)		
	Mutation	G314D	G326E	I321T	F1538	L1024V	I1017F	H92R	G126S	S141F
Gene	GluCl1	GluCl3		VGSC		CHS1	PSST	cytb		
Population	%MAF (Mutant Allelic Frequency)									
Tu1	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.92	1.89	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tu2	0.00	0.00	0.39	0.00	0.74	0.40	0.00	0.41	0.00	0.00
Tu3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tu4	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tu5	0.00	0.00	54.45	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.74	100.00	0.00	0.00
Tu7	0.00	0.00	30.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tu8	0.00	0.00	16.10	1.65	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tu9	0.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00
Tu10	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00
Tu12	0.00	0.00	0.00	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tu13	0.00	0.00	0.00	4.64	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tu14	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tu15	0.00	0.00	0.00	31.41	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tu16	0.00	0.00	69.04	92.33	0.00	91.17	0.00	92.79	0.00	0.00
Tu17	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tu18	0.00	0.00	10.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tu19	0.00	0.00	N/A	42.71	0.00	100.00	47.77	100.00	0.00	42.89

Table 4 Mutant allele frequencies measured by ddPCR in pools of *B. tabaci* field populations

Acaricide class (active ingredient)	AChE inhibitors (OPs, carbamates)	Sodium channel modulators (Pyrethroids)		Lipid biosynthesis inhibitors targeting ACC (tetronic & tetramic acid derivatives / ketoenols))
Mutation	F331W	L925I	T929V	A2083V
Gene	<i>Acel</i>	<i>VGSC</i>		<i>Acc</i>
Population	%MAF (Mutant Allelic Frequency)			
Bt1	92.44	34.36	58.24	88.41
Bt2	89.64	35.72	56.48	89.82
Bt3	21.48	2.90	10.73	1.39
Bt4	95.56	31.65	51.83	71.43
Bt5	89.30	37.49	57.94	78.12
Bt6	92.11	44.74	45.29	92.74

Supplementary Table S1. Collection details of *Tetranychus urticae* (Tu1–Tu19) and *Bemisia tabaci* (Bt1–Bt6) field populations, including locality, host plant, and date.

Population	Locality	Host Plant	Collection Date
Tu1	Trypia/Aigion, Achaia Prefecture	Lemon	19 September 2023
Tu2	Elaionas/Aigion, Achaia Prefecture	Lemon	2 October 2023
Tu3	Leukakia, Argolida Prefecture	Orange	9 November 2023
Tu4	Kalitheia, Argolida Prefecture	Tangerine	10 November 2023
Tu5	Tympaki, Heraklion Prefecture	Pepper/Eggplant	23 November 2023
Tu6	Kalyviani, Heraklion Prefecture	Pepper	1 February 2024
Tu7	Ampelouzos, Heraklion Prefecture	Eggplant	6 February 2024
Tu8	Ampelouzos, Heraklion Prefecture	Rose	6 February 2024
Tu9	Terpsithea/Kyparissia, Messinia Prefecture	Eggplant	1 June 2024
Tu10	Faraklasda/Kyparissia, Messinia Prefecture	Cucumber	1 June 2024
Tu11	Agia Kyriaki/Kyparissia, Messinia Prefecture	Watermelon	1 June 2024
Tu12	Marathoupoli/Kyparissia, Messinia Prefecture	Mellon	1 June 2024
Tu13	Fourni, Lasithi Prefecture	Various Vegetables	30 June 2024
Tu14	Neapoli, Lasithi Prefecture	Various Vegetables	30 June 2024
Tu15	Kalessa, Heraklion Prefecture	Zucchini	22 July 2024
Tu16	Tympaki, Heraklion Prefecture	Zucchini	24 July 2024
Tu17	Krousonas, Heraklion Prefecture	Tomato	31 July 2024
Tu18	Tympaki, Heraklion Prefecture	Zucchini	7 October 2024
Tu19	Tympaki, Heraklion Prefecture	Eggplant	21 January 2025
Bt1	Tympaki, Heraklion Prefecture	Eggplant	24 July 2024
Bt2	Tympaki, Heraklion Prefecture	Tomato	24 July 2024
Bt3	Kalessa, Heraklion Prefecture	Cucumber	29 August 2024
Bt4	Moires, Heraklion Prefecture	Melon	9 July 2024
Bt5	Tympaki, Heraklion Prefecture	Pepper	21 January 2025
Bt6	Tympaki, Heraklion Prefecture	Eggplant	21 January 2025

*Refers to the last season prior population collection